

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Distributions and Constraints

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The Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions may be obtained directly by considering a power law (based on a function of one parameter) of a function $f(e_i/T)$ which becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for $e_i/T \ll 1$ as well as for a special value of the parameter, as well as a power law (e_i/T) power function of single parameter for $e_i/T \gg 1$. We show that if such a distribution becomes the MB distribution for a particular value of the parameter, then it must also become the MB distribution for $e_i/T \ll 1$. It is readily possible to create two distributions which satisfy these criteria. Given the distributions, however, one must associate them with $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ to normalize and with a constraint on energy in order to find the value of T . This begs the question: Do these two distributions have any features linked to these two constraints or to another independent condition. We argue that if one chooses a linear function in e_i/T for $f(e_i/T)$, then one may show that for an appropriate energy constraint, this distribution is linked directly to the differentials of the two constraints. This is the Tsallis case. In the Kaniadakis case, we show that if one considers a quadratic equation for $e_i/T \ll 1$ for $f(e_i/T)$, then this is equivalent to the condition $p(e)p(-e) = 1$. In fact, using $p(e_i) = \text{odd function} + \text{even function}$, and choosing the simplest solution, one may directly obtain the Kaniadakis distribution. In other words, the condition $p(e)p(-e) = 1$ seems to go beyond the usual $\sum_i p(i) = 1$ and energy constraints.

Power Law Distributions

Imagine that one wishes to create a power law distribution:

$f(e_i/T)$ power function (single parameter) ((1)) such that it becomes $(-e_i/T)$ power function single parameter for $e_i/T \gg 1$

One may argue that the motivation is to match power law distributions seen in nature. At first, such a power law distribution may seem to have nothing to do with the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution.

We argue, however, that at least one power law distribution does have a direct link to the MB case. In fact, if one replaces the usual MB constraint:

$$\sum_i p(i) e_i \rightarrow \sum_i p(i) \text{ power } q e_i \quad ((2))$$

then one may use the same stability/maximization approach as that used for the MB case and obtain a power law solution which becomes the MB one in the $q=1$ limit. In particular, one first mimics the energy constraint (assuming that the two constraints contain all of the information in the problem) and write:

$$\sum_i p(i) \text{ power } q h(p(i)) \quad \text{such that } h(p(i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((3))$$

Then, changing $p(i) \rightarrow p(i)+dp(i)$, one requires that ((3)) have a 0 first order term for stability. This leads to a first term of:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ (} dp(i) \text{ power } q \text{) } h(p(i)) + \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) \text{ power } q \text{ } dh/dp(i) \quad ((4))$$

The first term is 0 because $h(p(i)) = -ei/T$ from d of the energy constraint and the second becomes zero if $p(i) \text{ power } q \text{ } dh/dp = 1$.

This leads to

$$h(p(i)) = 1/(1-q) \{ 1+ (1-q) p(i) \text{ power } 1-q \} \text{ if one wishes } h(p(i)) = \ln(p) \text{ for } q=1 \quad ((5))$$

Here one knows a priori that there must be a value of the parameter q , namely $q=1$, which restores the MB scenario.

Noting that $h(p(i))$ is the inverse of $p(i)$, one finds:

$$p(i) = (1+ (1-q)x) \text{ power } 1/(1-q) \text{ where } x= -ei/T \quad ((6)) \text{ unnormalized}$$

A point we wish to make is that if one assumes that there exists a parameter value for which the power law becomes the MB distribution for all ei/T , then this must also hold for $ei/T \ll 1$. In such a case, however, one must have:

$$f(ei/T) = 1 - ei/T \text{ i.e. the parameter must disappear} \quad ((7))$$

Given that the most general form of $f(ei/T)$ is $1- b ei/T$ for $ei/T \ll 1$, then:

$$1-bei/T \text{ approx=} \exp(-bei/T) \text{ which is raised to the power } = \text{function}(q). \text{ Thus } b = 1/\text{function}(q).$$

If function q is $1/(1-q)$, then $b=1-q$ as in the Tsallis case. In fact, such a linear approximation for $ei/T \ll 1$ holds for all ei/T .

Thus, given that the power law distribution becomes the MB one for a special value of the parameter, one must also have it become the MB one for $ei/T \ll 1$. This means that if one considers the power of the power law in the form of $1/(1-q)$ or $1/k$, then ei/T must be multiplied by $(1-q)$ or k in $f(ei/T)$ at least in the $ei/T \ll 1$ limit.

We notice from the above that one obtains the Tsallis distribution by replacing p in $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) \text{ } ei$ with $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } ei \text{ } p(i) \text{ power } q$. In other words, one is really using the ideas needed to obtain the MB distribution, but with a different energy constraint. One may also notice that $f(ei/T)$ is actually the small ei/T form, namely $1+ (1-q)(-ei/T)$. Given that one could just as easily create a second order expansion of term, one may ask whether there is another power law distribution which matches the MB for both a special value of the parameter and $ei/T \ll 1$ and becomes a power law in ei/T for $ei/T \gg 1$.

The Kaniadakis Case

Given the Tsallis result of $p(i)$, we have argued that it is natural to ask whether one may create an $f(e_i/T)$ which is of the form of a quadratic expansion in e_i/T for $e_i/T \ll 1$. Can such a distribution yield the MB for both $e_i/T \ll 1$ and a special value of k as well as a power law in e_i/T for $e_i/T \gg 1$. If so, is such a quadratic form linked to a special condition, presumably beyond the Sum over i $p(i)=1$ and energy constraints?

A quadratic expansion may be readily written as:

$$f(e_i/T) = 1 - k e_i/T + .5 k k e_i e_i / T T \quad \text{where } 1/k \text{ is the power of } f \text{ for } e_i/T \ll 1 \quad ((8))$$

This expression which holds at $e_i/T \ll 1$ must become proportional to e_i/T for $e_i/T \gg 1$. A simple way to obtain this result is to use:

$$\sqrt{1 + k k e_i e_i / T T} - k e_i / T = f(e_i/T) \quad ((9))$$

The question then becomes: To what constraint or special condition does this map?

We argue that it maps to the special condition:

$$p(e)p(-e) = 1 \quad ((10))$$

which is not of the form of a usual constraint. To see that this is the case, consider:

$$p(e) = p_{\text{Odd}}(e) + p_{\text{Even}}(e) \quad ((11))$$

because any function may be written in terms of an odd and even function.

$$\text{Then: } p(e) = 1 / p(-e) = 1 / \{-p_{\text{Odd}}(e) + p_{\text{Even}}(e)\} \quad ((12))$$

The simplest odd function is e and the simplest even is 1 . Then:

$$p(e) = 1 + e \text{ approx} = 1 / (1 - e) \quad \text{one for } e \ll 1 \quad ((13))$$

This suggests one consider: $p_{\text{Odd}} = ke$ and $p_{\text{Even}} = g(1 + kke)$, where g is an unknown function. Then:

$$ke + g(1 + kke) = 1 / \{-ke + g(1 + kke)\} \quad ((14))$$

Multiplying numerator and denominator by $ke + g(1 + kke)$ means:

$$-kkee + g(1 + kke)g(1 + kke) = 1 \quad \text{or } g = \sqrt{1 + kke} \quad (\text{here } e \text{ is really } e_i/T)$$

In the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, this produces the second order correction to $\exp(-ke_i/T)$.

Thus, the Kaniadakis distribution uses $\sum_i p(i)=1$ and an energy constraint $\sum_i e_i p(i)=1$ to determine T , but also requires the condition $p(e_i)p(-e_i)=1$ which is not of the form of a constraint. It does not really seem to be of the form of a maximized function $p(i) h(p(i))$ whose differential matches the differential of the two constraints. Instead it is based primarily on $p(e)p(-e)=1$. This point is made in (1). Why should the Kaniadakis distribution be linked to the MB one for $k=0$? We suggest that given that the constraints used are linked with the MB solution which automatically allows for $p(e)p(-e)=1$ because $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_1+e_2)$, one is deviating from the this second condition, but only imposing $p(e)p(-e)=1$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one wishes to have power distribution in e_i/T (to a function of a single parameter) for $e_i/T \gg 1$, then $f(e_i/T)$ power function (single parameter) holds for all e_i/T . If one wishes a single parameter value to restore the MB solution, then the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit must also yield the MB case. (We prove this.) We show that one may obtain such a distribution by replacing the MB energy constraint with $\sum_i p(i) e_i^q$ and then writing $\sum_i p(i) h(p(i))$ such that $h(p(i)) = -e_i/T$ (i.e. this sum mimics the energy constraint). Making this result stable (i.e. differential of this sum equals the differentials of the constraints) yields the Tsallis solution. One may note that it is of the form: $(1+(1-q)(-e_i/T))$ power $1/(1-q)$ (unnormalized). This begs the question: Can one have a quadratic power series which satisfies the above criteria? The result is the Kaniadakis distribution, but we show that this quadratic form is really identical with the condition $p(e)p(-e)=1$ which is not of the form of a usual constraint. Thus, the Kaniadakis result does not follow so easily from maximization being equivalent to differentials of constraints.

References

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